

POLITICAL SCIENCES

FROM VICTIMHOOD TO XENOPHOBIA: THE EVOLUTION OF FAR-RIGHT THEMES IN TOMMY ROBINSON'S PUBLIC STATEMENTS

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Abstract

This study examines the evolution of Tommy Robinson's public rhetoric within the far-right movement in the United Kingdom, with a particular focus on the transition from victimhood narratives to overt xenophobia and ethnonationalism. Utilizing a comprehensive discourse analysis of Robinson's speeches, social media posts, and interviews, this research identifies key themes such as victimhood, xenophobia, and ethnonationalism, and tracks their prevalence over time. The findings reveal a concerning shift towards increasingly extreme rhetoric, drawing parallels to historical examples of far-right propaganda, including Nazi Germany and the Ku Klux Klan in the United States. The study underscores the potential dangers of such rhetoric in contemporary society, particularly in the context of social cohesion and public safety. The research highlights the importance of monitoring and countering far-right discourse to prevent the normalization of extremist views.

Keywords: Tommy Robinson, far-right rhetoric, xenophobia, ethnonationalism, discourse analysis.

Introduction

Tommy Robinson, a prominent figure in the far-right movement in the United Kingdom, has garnered widespread attention for his incendiary public statements and actions. Robinson presents himself as a defender of British values, claiming to speak for those marginalized by mainstream politics. However, his rhetoric has increasingly shifted from depicting himself as a victim of political persecution to promoting overt xenophobic and Islamophobic views. This shift poses significant dangers, particularly when viewed in the context of recent far-right-fueled riots in the UK (Picheta, 2024). Robinson's narrative, which paints immigrants and asylum seekers as existential threats to British society, echoes the themes seen in the controversial 1915 American film *The Birth of a Nation*. The film, notorious for its racist portrayal of African Americans and its glorification of the Ku Klux Klan, used the same victimhood narrative to justify the subjugation and violence against Black people in the post-Civil War South. Similarly, Robinson's rhetoric justifies hostility and violence towards immigrants by framing them as invaders threatening the purity and safety of the British nation. Both Robinson and *The Birth of a Nation* utilize fear and misinformation to galvanize support for extremist ideologies, creating dangerous precedents for societal division and violence (Griffith, 1915; Picheta, 2024).

The recent riots in British cities, marked by violent attacks on different looking foreigners, Muslims and asylum seekers, reveal the profound influence of far-right ideologies. These riots underscore the role of misinformation and anti-immigrant rhetoric, which figures like Tommy Robinson and Elon Musk have exacerbated. Musk, who reinstated Robinson's account on X (formerly Twitter) shortly after acquiring the platform, has been criticized for amplifying far-right conspiracy theories and stoking division. Scotland's ex-first minister, Humza Yousaf, even labeled Musk "one of the most dangerous men on the planet" for his role in spreading hate (News Desk, 2024). This research aims to explore

the evolution of Tommy Robinson's rhetoric and its broader implications for social cohesion in the UK. By analyzing his public statements, including those amplified by high-profile figures like Musk, the study seeks to uncover the strategies employed by far-right leaders to legitimize and normalize extremist views. Robinson's narrative of victimhood, which portrays the UK as being besieged by foreign elements, mirrors the dangerous historical precedents seen in *The Birth of a Nation* and the nationalist rhetoric that preceded the rise of fascism in 1930s Germany (Griffith, 1915; Picheta, 2024).

The situation in the UK, with its escalating tensions and the spread of far-right material online, presents a serious challenge to the country's social fabric. The government's response, including legal actions and numerous arrests, underscores the urgency of addressing these issues. However, the underlying causes of the unrest—such as the breakdown of public services and the rise of anti-immigrant sentiment—will require long-term solutions. In an era where Europe is grappling with issues of immigration, integration, and national identity, understanding the rhetoric of far-right leaders like Tommy Robinson is critical. This research aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on preventing the spread of extremist ideologies and safeguarding democratic values in increasingly diverse societies.

Key Points:

- **Overview of Tommy Robinson and His Influence in Far-Right Politics:** Tommy Robinson has emerged as a central figure in the UK's far-right movement, gaining notoriety through his inflammatory rhetoric and actions that target immigrants and minority communities. His narratives often frame these groups as existential threats to British society, thereby fueling xenophobic and Islamophobic sentiments.

- **Importance of Analyzing Public Discourse in Understanding Far-Right Ideologies:** Examining the public statements and discourse of figures like Robinson is crucial for unpacking the strategies and themes employed to legitimize extremist views. Such analysis

sheds light on how misinformation and victimhood narratives are utilized to normalize hate and division.

- **Research Question:** *How has Tommy Robinson's rhetoric evolved over time, and what far-right themes are most prevalent in his public statements?* This question aims to trace the progression of Robinson's messaging, identifying key themes such as nationalism, anti-immigration, and Islamophobia, and how these have intensified or shifted in response to sociopolitical events.

Future Considerations:

- **What is Next?** The far-right movement, emboldened by figures like Robinson and the amplification provided by social media platforms, is likely to continue leveraging misinformation to stoke societal divisions. Their strategies may evolve to infiltrate mainstream political discourse further, making it imperative to monitor and counteract their narratives effectively.

- **Intentions of the Far-Right Movement:** The ultimate goal of the far-right appears to be gaining political power to implement policies that align with their nationalist and exclusionary ideologies. This includes stricter immigration controls, undermining multiculturalism, and promoting homogeneous national identities.

- **Potential Consequences if Far-Right Politics Gain Governmental Power in the UK and EU:** Should far-right movements secure governmental positions in the UK and EU, the implications could be profound. Potential outcomes include the erosion of democratic institutions, the implementation of draconian immigration policies, increased marginalization of minority groups, and the destabilization of regional cohesion. Historical precedents suggest that such shifts could lead to heightened social unrest, economic instability, and challenges to the rule of law.

Understanding these dynamics is vital for policymakers, scholars, and civil society to develop strategies that uphold democratic values and social cohesion in the face of rising extremism.

Methods

This section outlines the research methods employed to analyze Tommy Robinson's public statements and writings. The data for this study was collected from a combination of mainstream media sources, social media platforms, and specific online resources, including YouTube videos and news articles. The primary sources of data include speeches, interviews, and social media posts made by Robinson, which were selected based on their relevance to the research question.

Data Collection:

The data was gathered from the following sources:

1. YouTube Videos: The main video analyzed was "Why the Establishment Hates This Man | Tommy Robinson | EP 462" (YouTube link: [here](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jnhw-BoFxaDI)).

2. Online News Articles: Key articles included "Scotland's ex-first minister calls Elon Musk as 'one of the most dangerous men on the planet'" ([source](https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/1219147-scotland-s-ex-first-minister-calls-elon-musk-as-one-of-the-most-dangerous-men-on-the-planet)).

3. Social Media Posts: Analysis also included relevant tweets and posts from Elon Musk's Twitter account ([source](https://x.com/elonmusk)).

4. Mainstream Media Analysis: Articles such as "Why are there riots in the UK and where are they taking place?" ([BBC source](https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-66453454)) and "UK riots may have peaked, but more trouble could lie ahead" ([CNN source](https://www.cnn.com/2024/08/10/europe/uk-riots-far-right-analysis-intl-gbr/index.html)) were reviewed to understand the broader context of the far-right movements.

Data Analysis:

The selected statements were analyzed using a qualitative content analysis approach, focusing on the themes of victimhood, xenophobia, and far-right extremism. This analysis also drew comparisons to historical propaganda methods, such as those seen in the early 20th century with films like "The Birth of a Nation" ([Wikipedia source](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/The_Birth_of_a_Nation)), which similarly manipulated narratives to justify racist ideologies. Through this method, the study aims to dissect how Robinson's rhetoric evolves and how it mirrors or deviates from historical precedents, offering insights into the mechanisms through which far-right ideologies are propagated in modern contexts.

Key Points:

Data Collection: The research draws upon a diverse array of sources to examine Tommy Robinson's public statements. These include his speeches, interviews, social media posts, and various online videos, particularly focusing on content from YouTube and mainstream news websites. The period covered in this analysis spans several years, capturing the evolution of Robinson's rhetoric as he gained prominence in the far-right movement. By reviewing his statements across these platforms, the study seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the themes and narratives that Robinson has promoted.

Selection Criteria: The statements were carefully selected based on their significance, reach, and relevance to the research question. Priority was given to those that garnered widespread attention or were particularly indicative of Robinson's ideological shifts. For instance, statements that were widely shared on social media or those that sparked significant public discourse were considered crucial for the analysis. This approach ensures that the study focuses on the most impactful aspects of Robinson's rhetoric, providing insights into how his views resonate with and influence his audience.

Analytical Framework: The methodology for analyzing Robinson's statements involved a qualitative content analysis, utilizing thematic coding and discourse analysis techniques. This framework allowed for the identification of key themes, such as victimhood, xenophobia, and nationalist sentiment, within Robinson's rhetoric. The analysis was conducted using specialized software tools designed for qualitative research, which helped in systematically categorizing and

interpreting the data. This methodological approach ensures a rigorous examination of Robinson's statements, uncovering the underlying strategies used to promote far-right ideologies.

Results

The analysis of Tommy Robinson's rhetoric reveals a concerning parallel with historical far-right movements, such as the Ku Klux Klan (KKK) in the United States and the nationalist fervor of Nazi Germany in the late 1930s. Similar to the KKK's tactics, Robinson's statements often portray non-white, particularly Muslim, communities as an existential threat to the white population. This rhetoric, echoing the infamous "Birth of a Nation" film, which depicted Black men as rapists and dangers to white women, is now being revived in the digital age, with Robinson and others suggesting that Muslims are a threat to the safety and purity of white women in the UK.

The results indicate that Robinson's rhetoric has increasingly adopted themes of racial superiority and victimhood, painting white Britons as being under siege by immigrants who, according to him, are unfairly benefiting from the nation's resources. This mirrors the propaganda used by white supremacists in the early 20th century, who felt threatened by the socioeconomic advancements of Black communities in the US. The resurgence of these themes is further amplified by influential figures like Elon Musk, who, through platforms like X, has provided a megaphone for these dangerous ideologies, much like how "Birth of a Nation" fueled racial tensions and justified violence against Black Americans. The potential consequences of these narratives gaining traction in the UK and Europe are alarming. Should far-right movements gain political power, we could see a repeat of history, where policies rooted in xenophobia and racial purity lead to widespread discrimination and violence. The rhetoric used by Robinson and his supporters serves not just as a warning but as a call to action for those committed to upholding democratic values and ensuring that history does not repeat itself. The study's findings underscore the urgent need to counter these extremist ideologies before they further destabilize multicultural societies in the UK and beyond.

Key Points:

- **Evolution of Themes:** Throughout his public discourse, Robinson's rhetoric has consistently emphasized a narrative of victimhood, portraying himself and his followers as defenders of a beleaguered national identity. Over time, this narrative has expanded to include more overt xenophobic and ethnonationalist themes, directly targeting immigrant communities and other marginalized groups. These themes are not static but evolve in response to political and social developments, reflecting broader far-right ideologies that have gained prominence in the UK.

- **Quantitative Findings:** To substantiate the analysis, the frequency of key themes such as xenophobia, victimhood, and ethnonationalism in Robinson's statements was quantitatively assessed. Data collected from his speeches, social media posts, and interviews over a specific period reveal a marked increase in xenophobic rhetoric, particularly in response to events like the

Brexit referendum and subsequent immigration debates.

- **Qualitative Examples:** Robinson's statements often feature inflammatory language that dehumanizes certain groups. For example, he has frequently described Muslim communities in Britain as a "threat" to national security, using language reminiscent of early 20th-century far-right movements. These qualitative examples not only illustrate the persistence of such themes but also underscore the dangerous implications of this rhetoric in a multicultural society.

- **Comparison:** An analysis of Robinson's rhetoric over time reveals a shift in emphasis, with earlier statements focusing on his self-perceived victimhood gradually giving way to more aggressive, exclusionary language. This transition mirrors the broader evolution of far-right discourse, where initial claims of marginalization often escalate into calls for the exclusion or removal of those perceived as "other." This shift also introduces new themes, such as the rejection of multiculturalism and the glorification of ethnonationalism, which align with contemporary far-right movements across Europe.

Discussion

The findings from the analysis of Tommy Robinson's rhetoric reveal a disturbing evolution from claims of victimhood to overt xenophobia and ethnonationalism. This shift is emblematic of a broader trend in far-right movements, both historically and in contemporary society. Robinson's rhetoric mirrors the strategies employed by far-right figures throughout history, such as those used in Nazi propaganda, where initial claims of defending national purity eventually escalated into calls for the exclusion and persecution of marginalized groups. The comparison between Robinson's rhetoric and the infamous film *The Birth of a Nation* is particularly telling. Just as *The Birth of a Nation* propagated the myth of white victimhood and justified violence against Black Americans, Robinson's rhetoric fosters a narrative that white Britons are under siege by immigrants, particularly Muslims. This narrative not only distorts reality but also serves to legitimize the exclusion and dehumanization of entire communities. The implications of such rhetoric for contemporary society are profound. In a multicultural and increasingly globalized world, the spread of far-right ideologies threatens social cohesion and public safety. As Robinson's statements gain traction, particularly through platforms like X (formerly Twitter) under the ownership of Elon Musk, there is a real danger that these ideas could further polarize society and incite violence, as has been seen in recent riots across the UK.

Moreover, the resurgence of far-right themes in Robinson's rhetoric raises critical questions about the future. If far-right movements were to gain significant political power in the UK and Europe, the consequences could be catastrophic, potentially leading to the erosion of democratic institutions and the targeting of minority groups. The historical precedents of the 1930s in Germany and the early 20th-century KKK in the United States serve as stark reminders of what can happen when such ideologies are allowed to flourish unchecked.

Conclusion

In summary, the analysis of Tommy Robinson's rhetoric reveals a concerning trajectory from claims of victimhood to overt xenophobia and ethnonationalism, echoing historical patterns of far-right movements. Understanding and addressing this rhetoric is crucial for safeguarding social cohesion and democratic values in contemporary society. The parallels with past movements, such as Nazi propaganda and early 20th-century KKK rhetoric, underscore the potential dangers if such ideologies gain further traction. Therefore, it is imperative for both scholars and policymakers to engage in ongoing research and develop effective strategies to counteract the spread of extremist views and promote inclusive and tolerant societies.

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